

EFFECT OF MOISTURE CONTENT, PARTICLE SIZE AND FEEDING RATE ON THE PELLETING CAPACITY AND PELLETING EFFICIENCY OF A FLAT DIE LIVESTOCK FEED PELLETING MACHINE.

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Abstract

This study evaluates the impact of three critical parameters moisture content, particle size, and feeding rate on the pelleting capacity and efficiency of a flat die pelleting machine using soybean straw, pigeon pea husk and powder, and shredded maize. Experimental trials were conducted at Department of Renewable Energy Engineering, Dr. PDKV Akola. Using a Box-Behnken design to assess the individual and combined effects of the parameters. Moisture content varied between 25% and 35% (w.b.), particle sizes ranged from 1 to 3 mm, and feeding rates ranged from 110 to 120 kg/h. Results discovered that optimal pelleting capacity up to 118.86 kg/h and pelleting efficiency up to 93.9% were achieved at a moisture content of 30%, a particle size of 1 mm and a feeding rate of 120 kg/h. The study also identifies significant interactions between input variables and highlights the suitability of agricultural byproducts in sustainable livestock feed production. Statistical analysis using ANOVA confirmed the influence of all three parameters on pelleting performance at ($p < 0.05$). The research supports the economic viability and technical efficiency of using crop residues, dal mill waste by-product and shredded maize in pellet form for animal feed.

Keywords Pelleting machine, agricultural residues, feed efficiency, particle size, moisture content, feeding rate.

Introduction

Livestock production is heavily dependent on feed, which accounts for over 60% of total operational costs. Due to rising prices of concentrated feed materials and increasing competition for animal feed materials, the use of agricultural residues as an alternative feedstock has become a promising strategy. Pelleting enhances feed quality by improving density, digestibility, and handling properties. The quality and performance of pellets depend significantly on process parameters such as moisture content, particle size, and feeding rate.

India produces large volumes of agro-residues such as soybean straw dal mill by product such as pigeon pea husk and powder, and maize waste. These are underutilized and often discarded. Their valorization through pelleting not only adds economic value but also helps mitigate waste management challenges. This study investigates the effect of moisture content, particle size, and feeding rate on key output parameters, pelleting capacity, efficiency, pellet density, durability, and electricity consumption, for a flat die pelleting machine.

Materials and methods**Feedstock selection**

This study evaluated three types of feedstocks in which agricultural residues, soybean straw, dal mill waste by-product, pigeon pea husk and powder and shredded maize each selected for its availability and relevance to livestock feed:

Soybean straw: A fibrous residue from soybean harvesting, known for moderate bulk density and high lignocellulosic content.

Pigeon pea husk and powder: A byproduct of pulse milling, containing moderate fiber and relatively low energy density.

Shredded maize residue: Includes stalks and cobs, characterized by higher bulk density and moderate-to-high starch content.

All feedstock was collected from the department and local market, air-dried, and ground to sizes of 1 mm, 2 mm, and 3 mm. Moisture was adjusted to 25%, 30% and 35% (wet basis) by spraying calculated

water amounts, using a water-spraying method desired moisture content is maintained.

Experimental setup

The experimental trials were conducted using a flat die pelleting machine equipped with a 5 HP electric motor operating at 1440 rpm and fitted with a 8 mm diameter die. Feed rate was varied at 110, 115 and 120 kg/h. in department of renewable energy engineering. The machine's energy use was monitored using a calibrated digital energy meter. All experiments were performed in three replicas to check accuracy and statistical reliability of the observed results.

Measured parameters

Pelleting capacity (kg/h): Measured by dividing the total mass of pellets by processing time.

Pelleting efficiency (%): Ratio of pellets obtained to the input mass, expressed as a percentage.

Pellet density (kg/m³): Calculated by dividing pellet mass by volume.

Durability (%): Determined using a tumbling box method.

Electricity consumption (kWh): Measured using an energy meter.

Data Analysis

Statistical analyses including ANOVA and regression modelling were performed using Design-Expert software. Optimization was conducted through response surface methodology (RSM).

Results and discussion**Experimental results**

The pellet characteristics play an important role in various unit operations namely their handling, storage and transportation before using as domestic and livestock feed. On the basis of optimised solution properties of pellets like pelleting capacity, pelleting efficiency, pelleting density, pelleting durability and electricity consumption are evaluated as per the standard method. The following table presents the comparative results for pelleting performance across all feedstocks. This expanded table provides a holistic view of how different feedstock affected pelleting outcomes.

Table 1: Experimental outcomes of pelleting machine

Feedstock	Pelleting Capacity (kg/h)	Pelleting Efficiency (%)	Pelleting Density (kg/m ³)	Pelleting Durability (%)	Electricity Consumption (kWh)
Soybean Straw	113.65	91.25	510.80	93.12	4.18
Pigeon Pea	113.65	91.92	536.85	88.75	3.62
Shredded Maize	101.87	88.40	559.82	88.42	4.07

Analysis by feedstock

Each feedstock responded differently to the set parameters, revealing distinct trends. Soybean straw's fibrous nature allowed for improved compression and durability under optimal conditions. Pigeon pea, being slightly less fibrous, flowed more easily, reducing energy consumption. Shredded maize had high bulk density, leading to more

compact pellets but at slightly reduced efficiency. These differences are critical when selecting feedstocks for specific pelleting goals, such as maximizing output or minimizing energy use.

Soybean straw: Showed highest pelleting efficiency and durability. The optimal conditions were 32 % moisture, 1 mm particle size, and 120 kg/h feed rate.

Pigeon pea: Had the lowest electricity consumption. Optimized at 31 % moisture, 1 mm particle size, and 118 kg/h feed rate.

Shredded maize: Achieved highest pellet density. Optimal performance at 25 % moisture, 1 mm particle size, and 119.

ANOVA and statistical significance

Detailed ANOVA results indicate that moisture content had the most significant influence on capacity and durability, while particle size was strongly associated with density. Feed rate notably affected electricity consumption and efficiency. Two-way interactions, particularly between moisture content and feed rate, emerged as highly significant ($p < 0.01$), suggesting that balancing these two parameters is essential for optimal machine performance.

ANOVA analysis confirmed significant impacts ($p < 0.05$) of moisture content, particle size, and feeding rate on all performance metrics. The interaction between moisture content and feeding rate showed particularly strong influence on efficiency and electricity use.

Conclusion

The flat die pelleting machine demonstrated high performance with optimized values of 30–32% moisture, ~1 mm particle size, and feed rates around 120 kg/h. Soybean straw delivered the highest efficiency

and durability, shredded maize the highest density, and pigeon pea the lowest electricity consumption. These results support the conversion of agricultural residues into durable, efficient livestock feed pellets.

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